

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Ichthyofaunal diversity of Banshelki Dam Udgir, Dist. Latur (M.S.)

Dhaswadikar Usha Sitaram *

Department of Zoology, Shri. Hawagiswami Mahavidyalaya, Udgir Dist. Latur, India.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2024, 23(03), 2956–2959

Publication history: Received on 17 August 2024; revised on 25 September 2024; accepted on 28 September 2024

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2024.23.3.2972>

Abstract

Ichthyofaunal diversity is good indicator of aquatic ecosystem. A diversity of fishes represents the balanced ecosystem. By taking this into consideration the ichthyofaunal diversity of Banshelki dam is studied during present investigation. The Banshelki Dam spread over area about 2290 m. The Dam is old and constructed on Manmod river. Total 20 species of fishes belonging to 13 genera, 06 families and 05 orders were identified from the Dam. The order cypriniformes was dominant among fishes.

Keywords: Ichthyopfauna; Diversity; Banshelki Dam

1. Introduction

Fishes are aquatic animals, adapted for aquatic life. Fresh water bodies comprises with variety of fish species. Human being uses fishes for many purposes. Many people are suffering from hunger and malnutrition, for whom fishes are rich source of food with nutritional value. Fishes have formed an important item of human diet from time immemorial and are caught for this purpose. (Sarwade and Khillare, 2010), In order to maintain sustainable development and stability of ecosystem, surveillance of fish faunal diversity of water bodies is needed. The workers like Kumble and Reddi (2012), Kharat et.al. (2012), Galib et. al (2013), Chandrashekhar (2014) and many more have contributed in the field of fish faunal diversity. Present study is attempt to study the Ichthyofaunal diversity of Banshelki Dam.

2. Material and Methods

The present investigation on Ichthyofauna is carried out on the Banshelki Dam from June 2009 to May 2010. The capacity of the Dam is 107.24 million cubic meters. The length and depth of this Dam is 2290 and 800 meter respectively. The catchment area of Dam is 22 sq.km. The dam is beneficial to Udgir city and remote area. The fishes from the Dam were collected with the help of local fishermen. The collected fishes were brought to laboratory, cleaned with rectified spirit and preserved in 10% Formalin. The fishes were identified by standard keys of Day (1878), Jayram (1981), Talwar and Jhingaran (1991) and (2005).

3. Result and Discussion

During present investigation 80 species of fishes belonging to 05 orders and 05 families were identified. (Table no.1) The family Cyprinidae was dominant among others. Total 08 species of fishes were observed belongs to order Cypriniformes and family Cyprinidae. Fresh water carps are included in this order. The second order observed was siluriformes, total 03 species were observed from this order.

* Corresponding author: Dhaswadikar Usha Sitaram

The common identification of these fishes is presence of one or two pairs of barbells. The 02 species belongs to family Notoptendar, 02 species belongs to Angullidae and two species belongs to Bagridae were also observed from the Dam. The economically important species of fishes like Labeo rohita, Catla Catla, Channa striatus, Channa Marulius and Tilapia mossambica were found more in dam during study period. It is due to the release of seedlings and fingerlings of these economically important fishes in Dam for commercial fishery practices.

The diversity and abundance of fishes in Banshelki Dam is depends on the availability of food and health of ecosystem over long period of time. It is also due to the controlled fishing practices at the Dam. Sakhare (2001) reported the 23 species of fishes belonging to 7 orders at Jawalgaon reservoir, Dist. Solapur (M.S.) The order Cypriniformes was reported to the dominant in terms of number of species.

Sarwade and Khillare (2010) reported the 60 species of fishes belonging to 15 families and 36 genera in Ujani Wetland (M.S.) Kamble and Reddi (2012) reported the 10 species of fishes belongs to 5 orders and 6 families. Kharat et.al (2012) had recorded 5 species belongs to 14 families and 35 genera during study period on Krishna River at Wai (M.S.) Jayabhaye and Lahane (2015) observed 21 species of fishes belongings to 6 families and 13 genera in Pimpaldari tank, Hingoli (M.S.)

Figure 1 Ichthyofaunal Diversity

Table 1 Fishes observed at Banshelki Dam

Sr.No.	Order	Family	Name of Fish
1	Clupleiformes	Notopteridae	<i>Notopterus, N.Chitala</i>
2	Cypriniformes	Cyprinidae	<i>Cyprinus Carpio, Catla Catla, Chela Phulo, Labeo Rohita, Ihulo Rabeo bata, Cirrihina mrigale, Rasbora, daniconius, puntius sarana, punius ticto, Garra mullya</i>
3	Siluriformes	Siluridae	<i>Wallayo attu, ompak callichronus, ompak pabda</i>
4	Channiformes	Chandiae	<i>Channa straitus, Channa marulius, Channa orientalis</i>
5	Perciformes	Bagridae	<i>Mystus seengala, Mystus cavassius</i>

4. Conclusion

The Banshelki Dam is good ichthyofaunal diversity Dam. It has represented by 20 of species of fishes belonging to 13 genera and 05 families and 05 orders.

The diversity and abundance of fishes in Banshelki Dam represents the suitable water for aquaculture practices. To maintain the richness of aquatic ecosystem continuous monitoring of Dam is needed.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgement

The author is thankful to Head, Dept. of Zoology and Principal, SHM Udgir for continuous help, support during research work.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

References

- [1] Kar D. (2003) in Environment Pollution and Management, APH Publishing Corporation, New Delhi (Kumar A., Bohra, C., Sing L.D. eds.), 2003.211
- [2] Mittermeier R.A., Mitemeir C.G. (1997) In Global freshwater biodiversity sea wind cemex Mexico City (Mc Allister D.E., Littamiltion A., Harvery B. eds.). 1-140
- [3] Hamilton-Buchanan (1822) Edinburg and London.
- [4] Jerdon T.C. (1849) Journal of Literature Science, 15, 302-346.
- [5] Bloch E. (1860) J. Asiat Soc. Bengal 29 (2), 138-174.
- [6] Datta A.K. and Majumdar N. (1970) Fishes Record. Zoological Society of India 62 (1 & 2), 63-100
- [7] Johai M.S., Tondon K.K. (1981) Res. Bull. Punjab University, 32, 143-154
- [8] Kaul M., Rishi K.K., Shah K.L. (1982), Punjab Fish. Bull. 6 (12). 24-27.
- [9] Dutta S.P.S., Malhotra Y.R. (1984), University Review, 2 65-92
- [10] Tilak R., Baloni S.P. (1984), Fishes Record. Zoological Society of India 81 (3 & 2), 255-272
- [11] Sen T.K. (1985) Fishes Record. Zoological Society of India 62, 216
- [12] Johai M.S. Rawal Y.K. (2000) In Proceedings 'Rational use of water resources for aquaculture', HAU, Hissar, Haryana (Garg S.K., Jain K.L. eds.) 150-160
- [13] Meshram C.B., Meshram V. (2005) J.Aquat. Biol. 20 (2). 77-78

- [14] Hiware C.J. (2006) Zoos, Print Journal 21 (1), 2137-2139
- [15] Abrue E.A. (1925) Zoological Survey of India, Calcutta
- [16] Hora S.L., Nair K.K. (1941) Record of Indian Museum, 43 (3), 361-373
- [17] Dubey G.P., Mehra R.K. (1962) In Proceedings of 1st All India Zoological Congress, Zoological Society of India, 647-665
- [18] Dubey G.P., Varma M.N. (1965), Vikram University Res. Bull, 8 (4) 01-08
- [19] Agarwal S.S., Saksena D.N. (1977) J. Jiwaji University, 5(2), 164-168
- [20] Saxena R., Shrivastava P. (1989) J. Inland Fish. Soc. India. 21 (2), 41-45
- [21] Rao K.S. Chatterjee S.N., Singh A.K. (1991), J. Inland Fish. Soc. India, 23 (1), 34-41
- [22] Shukla A.N. Pandey A., Shrivastava S. (2003) Aquacult, 4 (1), 15-21
- [23] Pathak S.K., Mudgal L.K. (2005) Environ. Conser. J. 6(1), 41-45
- [24] Trivedi S., Shrivastava S., Acharya S., Shukla A.N. (2005), Aquacuit, 6 (2) 143-147
- [25] Sharma S., Sharma P., Siddiqui A., Belsare D.K. (2007) Him. J. Environ. Zool. 21 (2) 349-352
- [26] Saksena D.N. (2007) in Fresh water fish diversity of central India. National Bureau of Fish Generics Resources. Lucknow (Lakra W.S., Sarkar U.K. eds.) 50-57
- [27] Rao R.J., Saksena D.N., Garg R.K., Singh B.D. (2007) In Fresh water fish diversity of central India. National Bureau of Fish Generics Resources. Lucknow (Lakra W.S., Sarkar U.K. eds.) 46-49
- [28] Garg R.K., Rao R.J., Saksena D.N., (2007) Zoos' Print Journal, 22 (8), 2801-2803
- [29] Dhakad N.K, Shinde D., Choudhary P. (2008) Nat. Environ. Poll. Tech. 7 (1), 159-161
- [30] Vyas A. Damde D., Parashar V. (2009), J. Acqul. Biol. 24 (1), 44-49.
- [31] Day F. (1889) Text and Atlas in 4 parts. London XX-778. 195 pls. London William Dawson and Limited.
- [32] Talwar P.K., Jhingran A.G. (1991) Oxford and IBH Publishing Company Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi.
- [33] CAFF (2006) Organized by NBFGR, Lucknow at Bhopal
- [34] Dubey P.K., Maheshwari L.P., Jain A.K. (1980), J. Jiwaji Univesity, 8 (2), 113-122
- [35] Shrivastava S. (1990) MPCST, Bhopal
- [36] Rao K.S., Kartha K.N., Shrivastava S., Pandya S.S., Choubey U. (1988) In Proceedings of National Symposium on past. present and future of Bhopal lake. 55-85
- [37] Shahnawaz A. Venkateshwarlu M. (2009), Cur. Biotica 3 (4). 232-243
- [38] CAMP (1998) Organized by Zoo Outreach Organisation and NBFGR, Lucknow.
- [39] Brraich O.S., Ladhal S.S. (2005) In Proceedings of the National Seminar 'New Trends in fish development in India', Punjab University, Chandigarh (Johal M.S. ed.) 47-52
- [40] Sreekantha M.D., Subhash Chandra, Mesta D.K., Rao G.R., Gururaja K.V., Ramchandra T.V. (2007) Cur. Sci. 92 (11), 1592-1603
- [41] Prasad D., Venkataramana A.G., Thomas M. (2009), J. Environ. Biol. 30 (5), 713-718
- [42] Thirumala S., Kirab B.R., Kantaraj G.S. (2011), Adv. Appl. Sci. Res. 2 (5) 34-47.